

1 **Cyclin activation during resistance in TNBC.**

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7 We describe cyclin activation during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC. *CCNL1* was most abundantly
8 activated. This occurred concomitant with CDK silencing, including *CDK6* repression.

9 Citations

10 1. O'Brien, S., Kelso, S., Steinhart, Z., Orlicky, S., Mis, M., Kim, Y., Lin, S., Sicheri, F. and Angers, S.,
11 2022. SCF^{FBXW7} regulates G2-M progression through control of CCNL1 ubiquitination. EMBO reports,
12 23(12), p.e55044.